

COMPOSITE-WATER INTERACTIONS: SORPTION AND POROSITY IN AN EPOXY RESIN

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ABSTRACT

Moisture sorption and desorption of an uncured epoxy resin, monitored at different relative humidities using a thermo-gravimetric method, yielded an anomalous isotherm and a diffusion coefficient that decreased with increasing water concentration. The deviation from ideal solution behaviour is reflected with changes in the Flory-Huggins interaction parameter and compared to Henry's law. The results from the analysis indicate that water molecules form aggregates or clusters which are initiated at sites on the epoxy molecule. Experimental evidence supports the conclusion that such clusters are relatively less mobile than isolated water molecules. Preliminary results are presented that show air bubbles, entrapped in resin that had been exposed to a humid environment, can grow due to the diffusion of water.

INTRODUCTION

Moisture sorption in composite materials has been of interest to many investigators as the presence of water within the system can have severe, detrimental effects on the mechanical properties of the final composite^{1,2}. In terms of processing, water can act as a catalyst initiating premature curing thus reducing the shelf-life of the resin formulation and affect the degree of cure by reacting with the functional groups required for the crosslinking reaction³. Many of the polymer groups responsible for good composite performance are also hydrophilic. Experiments have also shown that laminates made from pre-impregnated fibre sheets (prepreg), which were exposed to low humidity environments, exhibited considerably less porosity than those exposed at higher relative humidities, while those subjected to hygrothermal soakings resulted in extreme porosity⁴.

Water can enter a composite system in several ways; diffusion and solubility of water into the resin from humid air during the resin mixing operation, moisture adsorbed onto the surface of the plies due to the affinity of the epoxy molecule for water and humid air entrapment in the form of bubbles. Since a composite will be accessible to water at some stage along the processing route (even the commercial preparation of the epoxy precursor involves washing the resin to remove unwanted products) the resin will have some finite water concentration before being committed to the cure cycle unless rigorous measures are taken. Although degassing the resin under vacuum will aid the removal of water (by reducing the ambient pressure below the water vapour pressure), maintaining low humidities in a production environment may be prohibitively expensive so a knowledge of the sorption process is imperative to the production of a high quality composite.

This work describes a series of experiments that were performed on an uncured epoxy resin that was exposed to different humid environments. The resulting isotherm and analysis provide information on the water molecules within the polymer and how their mobility is affected by these interactions. Preliminary results are presented to show that air bubbles, entrapped in a resin exposed to a humid environment, will grow due to the diffusion of water into the bubble.

SORPTION IN POLYMERS

The simplest case of sorption is that of an ideal solution with the sorbed species randomly dispersed within the polymer such that Henry's law is obeyed. The solubility is then a constant, independent of sorbed concentration, at a given temperature and the sorption isotherm is a linear relation of concentration vs. pressure (partial pressure). When sorption is influenced by site interactions such that polymer-penetrant interactions are favoured the sorbed concentration increases until the sites are occupied⁵. Subsequent penetrating molecules can then dissolve with a more or less random distribution. In some cases the sorbed concentration increases continuously with pressure. This can be interpreted in two ways: (i) the first molecules to enter the polymer loosen the structure (plasticisation or swelling) which enables subsequent molecules to enter the polymer more easily⁶ (ii) penetrant-penetrant interactions are inherently stronger than the corresponding polymer-penetrant interactions such that association or clustering of the penetrant occurs within the polymer. These last two scenarios can be distinguished by the concentration dependence of the diffusion coefficient of the penetrating molecules in the polymer. In the case of a penetrant that plasticises or swells the polymer the diffusion coefficient will increase with increasing concentration⁷ while the converse is true for associated molecules where aggregates of molecules or clusters would be expected to be relatively less mobile than isolated molecules^{8,9}.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The resin used in this investigation was an unmodified liquid bisphenol-A/epichlorohydrin resin (Shell Epikote 828) with an epoxy group content¹⁰ of 5.128 moles/kg. The density of the resin was 1160kg/m³ at room temperature. A gravimetric method was used to determine the water uptake of the resin. The resin was thoroughly degassed and dried in a vacuum oven at 333K until all suspended bubbles were removed. Volatile weight losses, measured using a thermal balance with an accuracy of 1x10⁻⁴g, were found to be minimal (< 0.1%) after the degassing operation. The resin, after this procedure, was considered to be a base for the subsequent experiments.

The dry resin (0.2ml) was injected using a syringe into a glass cuvette of dimensions 10 x 10mm and the initial weight was recorded on an independent microbalance. The geometry was the same for all samples. The cuvette was placed in the thermal balance and the samples were then conditioned by exposure to humid environments. Blank samples were also tested. The thermal balance recorded the weight change with time which was plotted simultaneously on a chart recorder. All experiments were performed at 293K. The relative humidities (RH) were created by means of saturated salt solutions. Several lists of relative humidities over saturated solutions have been compiled¹¹ and a number were selected to monitor the moisture pick-up over the full relative humidity range.

The specimens were placed on the balance which was housed in a tubular oven. Air was passed through the salt solutions using a small pump and the resulting humid air was passed over the sample at a constant rate. The relative humidity of the air passing out of the furnace was

monitored intermittently using a wet-and-dry-bulb hygrometer. Sorption and desorption were monitored in most cases. With sorption the system was considered to be at equilibrium when there was no detectable weight change over a time period equivalent to attain that weight change. Desorption was attained by passing dry air through the chamber. Although zero relative humidity was not achieved in the chamber all samples were desorbed at a similar humidity (~12%).

Air bubbles were injected into a resin that had been exposed to a relative humidity of 54% using a hypodermic syringe. The bubbles were retained in the resin by a glass slide and the radius was monitored with time by optical microscopy.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The microbalance chart records of weight change against time were sampled at appropriate intervals and plots of fractional uptake against the square root of time were constructed. The mass uptake (M_t) at any time t is the mass increase per initial mass of the dry resin. The fractional uptake (M_t/M_∞) is the fraction sorbed at a time t with respect to the uptake at equilibrium. Figure 1 shows such a plot for sorption at 54% relative humidity.

Figure 1. Fractional moisture sorption and desorption at 54% relative humidity exposure.

Figure 2. Sorption isotherm showing the experimental data, the interaction from the inverse isotherm (—) and the notional Henry's law isotherm (. — . —) from eq.2.

The equilibrium sorption (weight %) was plotted against relative humidity exposure (RH%) and was found to exhibit an anomalous isotherm. The equilibrium sorption levelled out to a finite value of 4.68wt% at unit activity (100%RH). The isotherm clearly shows that the resin will have a finite water concentration of between 0.6wt% and 1wt% in a typical storage environment (30-60%RH) (figure 2). Middle range humidities exhibited a possible plateau with downward curvature at progressively lower humidities. This implies that resin-water contacts are strongly preferred which can be represented by dual-mode theory, i.e. the total solubility can be split up into contributions from Henry's law mode (ideal dilute solution behaviour) and a Langmuir-type mode^{5,12}. The change of slope at 55-65% RH can not be described by such a model which indicates that another mode of sorption is dominant. If normal solution was the dominant mechanism then it could be represented by a solution model such as that described by the Flory-Huggins theory¹³. The isotherm from the Flory-Huggins model is described by,

$$\frac{p}{p_0} = \phi_1 \exp(\phi_2 + \chi \phi_2^2) \quad (1)$$

where ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are the volume fractions of penetrant and polymer, respectively and χ is the Flory-Huggins interaction parameter. p/P_o is the vapour activity (where P_o is the saturated vapour pressure at the isothermal temperature) which, in the case of water, is the relative humidity/100. The Flory-Huggins model predicts that Henry's law is obeyed as ϕ_1 approaches zero.

Experimental data on water sorption by polymers can be based on some form of Henry's law, i.e. a measure of the quantity of water sorbed per unit quantity of polymer is plotted against the activity of water in the surrounding vapour. For a large number of polymers, a plot of the reciprocal of water sorption against the reciprocal of partial pressure exhibits near linear behaviour¹⁴. With the expectation that the volume fraction of water will be the expression of water concentration relevant to basic polymer solution thermodynamics, this measure has been used. This has been considered to be a better parameter than mole fraction when dealing with molecules that have significantly different molecular volumes, although a variety of expressions of concentration can be used which will alter the slope and intercept but not the linearity of the plot. It can be seen that the data is reasonably represented by a linear function (figure 3) and the limiting or infinite dilution isotherm, as the activity approaches zero, is given by the inverse Henry's law expression,

$$\frac{1}{\phi_H} = \frac{k_1}{\left(\frac{RH}{100}\right)} \quad (2)$$

k_1 is the proportionality constant (slope in figure 3) and ϕ_H is the volume fraction of water in the Henry's law mode.

Using the value of 91.75 for k_1 (determined by a linear regression through the experimental points), the equation is plotted as the upper line in figure 3. Graphically this is done by drawing a line parallel to the experimental data passing through the origin. The inverse of this relationship is the notional Henry's law isotherm which has been replotted on the original isotherm (figure 2). This is clearly an approximation as the experimental points deviate from linearity at low pressures (low activity). The deviation seems to occur between the reciprocal activity of 2 and 3 which corresponds to between the 33% and 50% relative humidity exposure, i.e. the plateau on the original isotherm. It is assumed that a linear relationship prevails in the following analysis.

It is assumed that at infinite dilution the behaviour of water is normal, representing the true interaction of water and resin molecules. If water sorption occurs on two types of site, a resin site and a resin-water site, the influence of the former will predominate as the partial pressure of water and the amount of sorbed water simultaneously approach zero. Hence using the limiting (Henry's law) approximation to the Flory-Huggins theory the interaction parameter is¹³,

$$\left(\frac{RH}{100}\right) \approx \phi_1 \exp(1+\chi) \approx k_1 \phi_1$$

$$\chi = \ln k_1 - 1 \quad (3)$$

This limiting value at zero activity can now be plotted with those determined by substituting the experimental values of the equilibrium sorption (in terms of volume fraction) in equation 1 with their corresponding activities (RH/100) (figure 4). It can be seen that χ is a decreasing function of concentration (figure 4). If the solution was completely random then the Flory-Huggins parameter would be constant over the activity range. It can be concluded that the changing χ

reflects deviations from ideal (random) mixing. The magnitude of χ implies that the water and the epoxy resin are not soluble under these conditions ($\chi \gg 0.5$)¹³.

Figure 3. Inverse plot of sorption isotherm showing the notional Henry's law isotherm. (slope = k_1 , intercept = k_2)

Figure 4. Flory-Huggins interaction parameter χ vs. water activity with infinite dilution value from eqs. 1 and 3.

Another measure of the deviation from ideality is to compare the isotherm to that predicted by the Henry's law isotherm. The ratio (N_e) of the total volume fraction to that in the Henry's law mode gives a measure to which the sorption of water is increased by the abnormalities of the sorption process which result from non-random mixing. Hence this enhancement¹⁴ can be described by,

$$N_e = \frac{\phi_1}{\phi_H} = \frac{k_1}{(k_1 - k_2 \left(\frac{RH}{100}\right))} = 1 + k_2 \phi_1 \quad (4)$$

where k_2 is the intercept of the inverse isotherm (figure 3).

Equation 4 indicates that the degree of deviation from Henry's law continually decreases with lower water contents and approaches Henry's law as the water concentration approaches zero, i.e. $N_e=1$. If the abnormalities of the isotherm are due to aggregation or clustering of water molecules in the resin then it is also anticipated that the such clusters will be less mobile than isolated water molecules.

The diffusion coefficient D was determined from the initial slope of the fractional plots and from the time to attain 50% of the total moisture uptake. The one dimensional case of Fick's second law was applied and no corrections for edge effects were required as the cuvette was impermeable to moisture¹⁵. The diffusion coefficient was calculated from,

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = \frac{4(Dt)^{1/2}}{L(\pi)^{1/2}} \quad (5)$$

where L is twice the thickness of the specimen¹⁶.

The plot of diffusion coefficient (from the half time measurements) vs. equilibrium concentration was found to be concentration dependent (figure 5). The diffusion coefficient was found to decrease by approximately an order of magnitude for a gain of 1wt% (<65%RH). At higher

relative humidities the diffusion coefficient was found to level off over the rest of the concentration range.

The diffusion coefficient was determined from the total sorbed concentration which implies that as the sorbed concentration increases the diffusion coefficient will decrease if a proportion of the molecules are less mobile. In the simplest case it can be assumed that all water in excess of that dictated by the Henry's law isotherm is immobilised either by interacting with the resin or by forming aggregates or clusters by association. If the concentration of free to diffuse molecules is denoted by C^* and the total concentration by C , then $D = D^*(dC^*/dC)$. D is the measured diffusion coefficient and D^* is the diffusion coefficient of the mobile molecules. D will only equal D^* when all the sorbed penetrant molecules are mobile, otherwise D will be less than D^* . If the enhancement number (N_e) is used as a measure of the concentration ratio of mobile molecules to the total number of molecules then,

$$D = D^* \left(\frac{1}{N_e} \right) \tag{6}$$

The limiting value of the diffusion coefficient ($7 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$) at $C=0$ was assumed to be the diffusion coefficient of the mobile concentration (D^*) and was determined by linearly extrapolating the low activity data (the mean value of sorption and desorption was taken at each activity). This rather arbitrary value is a possible explanation for the only adequate representation of the data in figure 5. The difficulty in specifying the diffusion coefficient at $C=0$ is primarily due to the fact that differences in the rate of sorption and desorption are more apparent at lower activities, e.g. 22%RH (the lowest concentration in figure 5). Nevertheless, the representation of the isotherm data and the concentration dependence of the diffusion coefficient is consistent with the concept of immobilisation and clustering.

The Flory-Huggins interaction parameter could also be used to in a similar way to determine the concentration dependence of the diffusion coefficient. The Flory-Huggins interaction parameter χ also decreases with increasing concentration although this will be a less sensitive indicator to clustering. The Flory-Huggins model for polymer-penetrant systems implies random mixing of the penetrant in the polymer. This random mixing includes penetrant-penetrant interactions which may be reasonably termed clusters. Deviations in χ will therefore reflect deviations from Flory-Huggins behaviour which infers deviations from random mixing.

Figure 5. Concentration dependence of water diffusion coefficient in the resin from half-time measurements. Solid line is from eqs.4 and 6.

Figure 6. Normalised radius² vs. time for an air bubble in resin that had been exposed to 54%RH. Solid line shows linear regression.

Figure 6 shows the growth of an air bubble entrapped in a moist resin (~1wt%) and monitored over time at 293K. The linearity of the plots indicate that diffusion is the mechanism for growth¹⁷. Air bubbles in "dry" resins collapsed with time^{18,19} which indicates that for the case in figure 6 water is the diffusing species since all other volatile components had been removed in the degassing operation. Attempts to determine the driving force (concentration gradient) for growth from a knowledge of the growth rate and the diffusion coefficient of water molecules in the resin indicate that the concentration of water actively involved in the diffusion process is much lower than the water concentration in the bulk resin. It is considered that such experiments also support the conclusion that water is immobilised in the resin.

CONCLUSIONS

The moisture uptake of the uncured epoxy resin clearly exhibits an anomalous isotherm and a diffusion coefficient that decreases with increasing concentration. The diffusion coefficient indicates deviations from ideal mixing in that such transport processes would be invariant with concentration if water was molecularly dispersed in the resin. The decrease in diffusion coefficient can be explained in terms of immobilisation of species, i.e. if the proportion of immobilised water increases with concentration then the diffusion coefficient will decrease as the concentration of mobile molecules to the total concentration decreases. It can therefore be supposed that the water enters the resin and is immobilised by interacting with the resin molecule and by association. This is not only evidenced by the decreasing diffusion coefficient but also by the plateau on the isotherm at middle range activities, the upward curvature of the isotherm at higher activities and the strong associative nature of water in the liquid state. The Flory-Huggins interaction parameter reflects the non-idealities of the isotherm while the inverse isotherm and the calculated enhancement number (N_e) directly represent deviations from ideal mixing. The concentration dependence of the diffusion coefficient is adequately represented by a simple model utilising this enhancement number. The qualitative mechanism suggested by the data and its interpretation is that at low concentrations water is distributed throughout the resin but preferentially on the epoxy molecule. At higher water concentrations the molecules begin to cluster together presumably at these sites. Preliminary experiments show that the presence of water in the uncured system is deleterious to the production of void free composites.

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